

A Solvent-Free Dispersion Method for the Preparation of PET/MWCNT Composites

Gonzalo Santoro, Marian A. Gómez, Carlos Marco, Gary Ellis*

A simple, easily accessible solvent-free method for the dispersion of MWCNTs into PET is proposed, based on the preparation of a microparticulate polymer/nanotube masterbatch via cryogenic impact-milling and its subsequent melt blending with the bulk polymer. Thermal and mechanical properties of nanocomposites prepared using this method were evaluated as a function of nanotube concentration. Thermal stability was improved, and superior crystallization behavior of PET in the nanocomposites was observed. Significant improvements of around 25% in tensile strength and tensile modulus of the nanocomposites was achieved using this strategy, with only 0.25 wt.-% MWCNT, compared to previous literature data where 1 wt.-% MWCNT was employed.

Introduction

The discovery of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) has attracted much attention in different areas of the scientific community,^[1] from fundamental physics to materials engineering. The excellent electrical, thermal and mechanical properties, together with high aspect ratios and large surface areas,^[2] make CNTs ideal candidates as reinforcements in the field of polymer nanocomposites.^[3] Several approaches have been employed to produce polymer/CNT nanocomposites, including conventional melt blending, solution mixing and in situ polymerization, amongst others. However, whilst significant advances have been made in these materials,^[4] the full potential predicted over the last decade is yet to be achieved.

One of the fundamental issues in optimizing the properties of polymer/CNT nanocomposites, and particularly the mechanical properties, is the efficient dispersion of

the nanoparticles within the polymer matrix.^[5] To overcome this, several strategies based on the chemical or physical modification of the CNTs have been developed with a view to improving interactions between the nanotube and the polymer,^[6] and good dispersions achieved.^[7] However, the development of industrially viable methods for the production of polymer/CNT nanocomposites, implying ease of scale-up, elimination of solvent-based pre-processing and low cost, is fundamental to the success and implementation of these materials, especially in the area of consumer and technical thermoplastics.

A number of recent studies have employed conventional pre-processing strategies to improve the efficiency of dispersion of nanotubes within polymeric matrices. Both Xia et al.^[8] and Masuda et al.^[9] used solid-state shear pulverization techniques to prepare poly(propylene)/CNT nanocomposites showing good dispersion of the CNTs and enhanced mechanical properties of the final materials.

On the other hand, poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) is one of the most widely used thermoplastic polyesters. PET exhibits various excellent properties including chemical and heat resistance, dimensional stability, high stiffness

and strength that make it an important material widely used in areas of packaging films, beverage bottles and as an engineering polymer in the construction and electronics industries. The incorporation of CNTs into PET in order to obtain composites with enhanced properties is of significant interest, and several authors have reported the incorporation of both single-walled CNTs (SWCNTs) and multi-walled CNTs (MWCNTs) into PET matrices using diverse approaches including solution mixing, in situ polymerization, melt compounding and electrospinning.^[10–13] The functionalization of CNTs has also been used to improve the compatibility between CNTs and PET.^[14] These and other dispersion methods have been recently reviewed by Grady.^[15]

In this work we describe a simple, solvent-free dispersion method for the incorporation of MWCNTs into a PET matrix based on the preparation of a microparticulate masterbatch by impact-milling at cryogenic temperatures. The masterbatch was subsequently melt blended with the polymer matrix to obtain composites with different CNT concentrations. We evaluated the effectiveness of this simple pre-dispersion method on the thermal and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites.

Experimental Part

Materials

The PET was supplied by Poliseda S.L. (Barcelona, Spain) in the form of pellets. Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) MWCNTs were purchased from Nanolab (Newton, MA, USA). The purity of the as-received nanotubes was higher than 95%, with average outer diameter of 5–15 nm and length ranging from 1 to 5 μm .

Masterbatch Preparation

Masterbatches with 15 wt.-% of MWCNT were prepared in powder form by cryogenic milling the as-received nanotubes together with polymer grains in a SPEX 6770 Freezer/Mill. The vial containing the sample and a metallic impactor was immersed in liquid nitrogen throughout the grinding process.

Composite Preparation

The PET/MWCNT nanocomposites were prepared by melt compounding the masterbatch and standard polymer pellets using an internal mixer Haake Rheocord 90 (60 cm^3). All materials were previously vacuum dried at 120 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h. The following blending conditions were used: temperature = 280 $^\circ\text{C}$, screw speed = 50 rpm and mixing time = 5 min. Nanocomposites at several nanotube concentrations from 0 to 1 wt.-% were prepared. After the melt compounding process, the samples were compression-molded for 5 min at 280 $^\circ\text{C}$ in a hydraulic press (Collin P200) and thermally quenched from the melt into ice water, forming 0.5 mm thick films.

Dumbbell-like specimens were cut from these films for the mechanical tests.

Characterization

The intrinsic viscosity ($[\eta]$), of the as-received polymer and the polymer powder generated by cryogenic milling was determined in 60/40 phenol/1,1,2,3-tetrachloroethane at 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ using an Ubbelohde viscosimeter. The molecular weight \overline{M}_v was calculated from the viscosity measurements using the Mark-Houwink equation:

$$[\eta] = K\overline{M}_v^a \quad (1)$$

with $K = 2.37 \times 10^{-4} \text{ dL} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$ and $a = 0.73$.^[16]

Raman spectroscopy was performed in the Raman Microspectroscopy Laboratory of the Characterization Service in the Institute of Polymer Science & Technology, CSIC, using a Renishaw *InVia* Reflex Raman system (Renishaw plc, Wotton-under-Edge, UK) employing a laser wavelength of 785 nm (laser power at sample = 1.6 mW; microscope objective = 50 \times).

Morphology was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using a Phillips XL30 microscope operating at 25 kV. All samples were coated with a 5 nm Au/Pd layer using a Polaron SC7640 sputter-coater. The composites were previously cryogenically fractured under liquid nitrogen.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was carried out using a Mettler TG50-TC10A thermobalance. The samples were heated from 50 to 750 $^\circ\text{C}$ at a rate of 20 $^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, in both nitrogen and air atmospheres, with a gas flow rate of 150 $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

The thermal behavior of the composites was studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) using a Mettler TA4000/DSC30-TC15 system under 30 $\text{cm}^3 \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ nitrogen flow. Aluminum DSC capsules containing samples of around 12 mg were heated to the melt and maintained at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min in order to eliminate the thermomechanical history, before quenching into liquid nitrogen. The following thermal cycles were then employed to study the thermal behavior. The samples were heated from 50 to 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ at 10 $^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, held for 5 min at 300 $^\circ\text{C}$ and then cooled to 50 $^\circ\text{C}$ at 10 $^\circ\text{C} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$.

The mechanical properties were measured at room temperature using an Instron 3366 universal testing machine with a 5 kN load cell, employing a constant crosshead speed of 1 $\text{mm} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ and a gauge length of 20 mm. The values of the mechanical properties represent the average of the results from at least five samples.

Results and Discussion

Masterbatch Characterization

It is extremely important to control the conditions of the milling process in order to minimize the damage provoked to the polymer. In this respect, several milling conditions were examined. In Table 1 the viscosity and \overline{M}_v of as-received PET and PET powder produced by three different milling cycles is presented. The PET was pre-cooled to liquid nitrogen temperature for 10 min, then subjected to a series

Table 1. Viscosity η and molecular weight \bar{M}_v of the milled PET

No. of cycles	$[\eta]$	\bar{M}_v
	$\text{dL} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$	$\text{kg} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$
0	0.70	57
3	0.68	55
6	0.65	52
12	0.61	47

of 3, 6 or 12 milling cycles at a frequency of 10 Hz, each of 2 min duration. Between each cycle, a 2 min delay was introduced to ensure that milling occurred at cryogenic temperatures. From the values in Table 1, a reduction in \bar{M}_v was observed with increasing number of milling cycles. Consequently, three cycles were employed for the masterbatch preparation.

The effect of the milling process on the nanotubes was evaluated using Raman spectroscopy (Figure 1). The ratio of the disorder-induced band (D-band: $1150\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the tangential mode (G-band: $\approx 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were used to estimate the purity of the nanotubes.^[17] A reduction in the ratio of intensities I_G/I_D from an initial value of 0.95 to 0.70 was observed, indicating some damage to the CNTs. Processing CNTs at room temperature by ball-milling has been shown to shorten the nanotubes and open their end caps, which could explain the decrease in the I_G/I_D ratio.^[18] On the other hand, the nature of the D-band has been used to qualitatively evaluate whether the damage provoked in the MWCNTs during the ball-milling process led to an increase in the amount of amorphous carbon, since the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of this band increases when the structural order of carbonaceous materials is lost.^[19] In our case, using a cryogenic impact milling process, no broadening in the D-band was observed and the FWHM of the D-band remained almost constant. This supports the hypothesis that the decrease in the I_G/I_D ratio is mainly due to a reduction in the length of the CNTs and to the appearance of defects, rather than the formation of amorphous carbon.

The morphology of as-received CNTs, milled CNTs, milled PET and the masterbatch were compared by SEM. Representative images are shown in Figure 2. The

Figure 1. Raman spectra of (a) as-received MWCNTs and (b) milled MWCNTs. The values of the intensity ratio between G and D bands as well as the full width at half maximum of the D-band are indicated in the Figure.

Figure 2. SEM images of (a) as-received nanotubes, (b) milled nanotubes, (c) and (d) milled PET and (e and f) masterbatch.

as-received material is a very dense network of highly entangled nanotubes (Figure 2a). The milled MWCNTs also present a very dense, entangled network and it is difficult to clearly distinguish any disentanglement effects due to the milling process (Figure 2b). On the other hand, the milled PET is a powdery material consisting of irregular grains with a wide size distribution, ranging from a few to some hundred nm, Figure 2c, with smooth surfaces produced by repetitive fractures at cryogenic temperatures (Figure 2d). The SEM images of the masterbatch, Figure 2e and f, show that the cryogenic milling process provoked an important level of nanotube disentanglement when prepared together with PET. Furthermore, the disentangled CNTs appear to be intimately wrapped around the polymer particles, demonstrating the effectiveness of the method to achieve a good initial mixture between the components.

Morphology of the Composites

The dispersion of the MWCNTs in the polymer matrix was also characterized by SEM (Figure 3). The micrographs obtained at low concentrations show isolated nanotubes, which appear as bright spots in the microphotographs, surrounded by the polymer matrix revealing that a good dispersion was achieved. With increasing concentration of CNTs in the matrix, isolated nanotubes were also encountered along with evidence of some zones where agglomeration of the CNTs was observed, due to the strong tube-tube interactions, showing that complete disentanglement of the nanotubes was not achieved.

Thermal Stability of the Composites

The thermal stability of the composites was studied by TGA. Thermal stability factors, such as the temperature at 10% of weight loss, T_{10} , the temperature at 50% of weight loss, T_{50} , temperature at the maximum decomposition rate, T_{mr} , and the residual yield at 700 °C, w_R , calculated from the weight loss curves in nitrogen are given in Table 2, and Figure 4 shows the integral and differential weight loss curves of the nanocomposites in nitrogen. The thermal decomposition of PET in an inert atmosphere involves

a chain scission process and the subsequent formation of a carbonaceous char that limits the diffusion of volatiles.^[20] The initial decomposition temperature was found to be only slightly affected by the presence of nanotubes. For concentrations below 1 wt.-% NTs, the effect of the nanotubes on the thermal stability is small, with only a slight increment found in the composite with the maximum amount of MWCNTs prepared. However, enhancement in the thermal stability becomes more significant at 1 wt.-% MWCNTs, where increments of 9 °C in T_{mr} and around 3.5% in w_R were found. Moreover, the differential weight loss curves manifest a reduction in the decomposition rate, also corroborating the thermal stability enhancement.

The thermal stability factors of the nanocomposites under airflow, including T_{10} , T_{50} , and the temperature at the maximum decomposition rate for the first and second degradation steps, T_{mr}^1 and T_{mr}^2 , respectively, are summarized in Table 2, and the differential and integral weight

Figure 3. SEM images of the nanocomposites. The concentration of NTs is indicated in each image.

Table 2. Thermal stability factors of the nanocomposites.

NT content wt.-%	N ₂ flow				Air flow			
	$T_{10}^{a)}$	$T_{50}^{b)}$	$T_{mr}^{c)}$	$w_R^{d)}$	T_{10}	T_{50}	$T_{mr}^{1)e)}$	$T_{mr}^{2)f)}$
	-C	-C	-C	%	-C	-C	-C	-C
0	412	439	438	10.56	409	437	436	562
0.1	412	440	438	10.95	409	438	436	561
0.25	412	440	440	11.10	409	437	434	556
0.5	413	443	443	12.42	409	438	440	556
1	416	447	447	14.01	412	447	447	613

^{a)}Temperature at 10% of weight loss; ^{b)}Temperature at 50% of weight loss; ^{c)}Temperature at the maximum decomposition rate; ^{d)}Weight residue at 700°C; ^{e)}Temperature at the maximum decomposition rate for the first degradation step; ^{f)}Temperature at the maximum decomposition rate for the second degradation step.

loss curves are depicted in Figure 5. In the case of the decomposition process in air, the thermal degradation of PET and its composites occur in two steps, the first associated with the aforementioned chain rupture and formation of char, and the second is a retarded degradation process due to the formation of more fragmented oxidative products.^[21] As in the case of the inert atmosphere, the incorporation of MWCNTs had little effect on the initial

decomposition temperature and only for 1 wt.-% NTs an increment in T_{10} was found. However, the effect of the nanotubes on both T_{mr}^1 and T_{mr}^2 indicates and enhancement of the thermal stability under air flow. The addition of 1 wt.-% nanotube content significantly enhances the thermal stability where an 118°C increase in T_{mr}^1 was observed, and the effect on the second degradation step was

Figure 4. Nanocomposites integral (upper) and differential (lower) weight loss curves under nitrogen flow.

Figure 5. Nanocomposites integral (upper) and differential (lower) weight loss curves under air flow.

Figure 6. DSC thermograms of the crystallization processes for PET and PET/MWCNT nanocomposites, (a) cold crystallization and (b) crystallization from the melt. The concentration of nanotubes is indicated above each curve.

an increase of 51.8°C in T^2_{mf} . Moreover the decomposition rate was reduced in both degradation steps indicating again an improvement of the thermal stability.

The aforementioned behavior can be attributed to an efficient dispersion of the CNTs into the PET forming an entangled network in the polymer matrix that hinders the diffusion of volatiles and leads to a subsequent enhancement in the thermal stability. The results obtained suggest that there is a threshold value in the concentration of MWCNTs for the formation of an entangled network that can lead to an efficient enhancement of the thermal stability. With the preparation method presented here the threshold is about 0.5 wt.-% for both atmospheres used.

Thermal Behavior of the Composites

DSC thermograms corresponding to the crystallization processes for heating and cooling cycles performed after quenching from the melt are presented in Figure 6, and characteristic features from the analysis of the DSC data

summarized in Table 3. The degree of crystallinity (X) was evaluated by the simple formula $(DH/DH_0) \times 100$, where DH is the apparent enthalpy of the selected transition and DH_0 is the enthalpy of 100% crystalline PET, taken as $140 \text{ J} \cdot \text{g}^{-1}$.^[22]

When the samples were heated immediately after quenching we observed that the incorporation of MWCNTs had little effect on the glass transition temperature, T_g , and the melting temperature, T_m of PET in the nanocomposites. However, the cold crystallization temperature, T_{cc} of PET decreased on incorporating the

nanotubes into the matrix, clearly indicating the existence of a heterogeneous nucleation phenomenon. T_{cc} was reduced by 13.8°C for as little as 0.1 wt.-% MWCNT, and remained practically constant for higher nanotube content. The heterogeneous nucleation effect was also observed in the dynamic crystallization from the melt, where an increase in T_c of 25.8°C was observed for the lowest concentration of 0.1 wt.-%, with only a slight increment in T_c for higher nanotube content. The nucleation process is also reflected in the crystallinity values obtained after quenching, X_{aq} , obtained from the difference between the enthalpies associated with the cold crystallization and melting processes in the same heating cycle.

The heterogeneous nucleation of PET with CNTs is known, and has been reported for both SWCNTs and MWCNTs. However, the effects observed in the nanocomposites prepared by the method proposed in this work are significantly greater, especially at low nanotube concentration. Anand and Agarwal^[12a] have reported an increment in the crystallization temperature of 15.8°C with a concentration of 1 wt.-% of non-functionalized SWCNTs.

Table 3. DSC results for the nanocomposites.

NT content wt.-%	Heating				Cooling			
	$T_g^a)$ -C	$T_{cc}^b)$ -C	$X_{cc}^c)$ %	$T_m^d)$ -C	$X_m^e)$ %	$X_{aq}^f)$ %	$T_c^g)$ -C	$X_c^h)$ %
0	82	137	25.8	258	35.8	10.0	196	35.6
0.1	82	124	24.4	258	37.5	13.1	221	39.2
0.25	82	122	23.8	258	38.7	14.9	223	39.8
0.5	82	123	22.8	257	37.8	15.0	222	40.0
1	81	121	16.4	257	36.1	19.7	223	40.8

^{a)}Glass transition temperature; ^{b)}Cold crystallization; ^{c)}Crystallinity associated with cold crystallization; ^{d)}Melting; ^{e)}Crystallinity associated with melting process; ^{f)}Crystallinity after quenching = $X_m - X_{cc}$; ^{g)}Crystallization from melt; ^{h)}Crystallinity associated with cooling process.

Yoo et al.^[14d] studied PET/MWCNT composites by a melt extrusion process at a nanotube concentration of 3 wt.-%, and obtained an increase of around 15 °C in T_c for composites prepared with both pristine and chemically modified nanotubes with different chemical treatments. Tzavalas et al.^[23], observed an increment of around 12 °C in T_c of PET with 0.1 wt.-% MWCNT incorporated by melt mixing, whereas the temperature increment in our case for the same concentration is more than double. This can be clearly attributed to a more efficient dispersion of the CNTs in the matrix offering higher surface area for crystal nucleation.

Mechanical Properties of the Composites

Although other factors such as the alignment of the nanoreinforcements or the interfacial stress transfer are clearly important, the enhancement of the mechanical properties depends mainly on the formation of an entangled network of nanotubes inside the matrix allowing the load to be efficiently transferred from the polymer to the nanoreinforcements.^[24] Achieving a good dispersion also minimizes the presence of zones where the stress is concentrated. Figure 7 shows the values of the mechanical parameters obtained from the tensile tests performed. The addition of nanotubes produced an enhancement in both the tensile modulus and the tensile strength at yield without making the nanocomposites more brittle than neat

PET. With the addition of only 0.25 wt.-% of CNTs the modulus and the tensile strength were increased by 24 and 26%, respectively, and increasing the concentration of MWCNTs did not produce further enhancement. Furthermore, the stress at break follows a similar trend to the tensile strength at yield up to 0.6 wt.-% MWCNTs, but at higher nanotube content a significant reduction is observed, albeit to a higher value than that for neat PET. However, whilst a practically constant value for elongation at break was observed, at the highest concentration of 1 wt.-% MWCNTs a reduction of over 20% was encountered. These are very promising data, since they clearly demonstrate that with efficient dispersion of the nanoparticles in the polymer matrix, relevant improvements in the mechanical properties can be achieved at lower nanotube content.

To our knowledge, the enhancements observed with the pre-processing strategy described in this work are the highest reported to date for PET/MWCNT nanocomposites prepared by a melt compounding process with non-functionalized nanotubes, and with the low concentrations employed, and are also higher than published results for nanocomposites prepared by other methods. Kim et al.^[12b] found an increase of 10–15% in the tensile modulus, and around 10% for the tensile strength at yield with the addition of 1 wt.-% of MWCNTs, whereas we obtained comparable results with a concentration of only 0.1 wt.-%. Jin et al.^[25] prepared PET/MWCNTs *via* in situ polymerization and found a decrease in both the modulus and the

tensile strength when the nanotubes were not functionalized. Ahn and Kang^[13] have reported an improvement of 9% in the tensile strength and 39% in the tensile modulus with the addition of 1 wt.-% MWCNTs, however they have prepared the composites by electrospinning, which implies the alignment of the nanotubes to some extent. The comparison of our results with previously reported data highlights the effectiveness of the dispersion method that we propose, not only due to the enhancement of mechanical properties, but also because of its potential industrial viability.

Conclusion

A simple, easily accessible solvent-free method for the dispersion of nanotubes in PET/MWCNT composites produced by a melt compounding process has been studied. This method consisted in the preparation of a masterbatch in powder

Figure 7. Results obtained from the mechanical tests of the nanocomposites. (a) Tensile modulus, (b) tensile strength, (c) stress at break and (d) elongation at break.

form by cryogenic impact-milling of both the PET and the MWCNTs, and subsequently melt blending with the polymer. The good dispersion achieved by this method is reflected by the enhancement of the properties of the composites with respect to neat PET, with special emphasis on the increase in T_c and the significant improvement of the mechanical properties with a very small nanotube concentration. The simplicity of the approach together with the low concentrations employed and the lack of the use of solvents make this method promising from an industrial point of view and it will be of great interest to study their extension to other polymers as well as the possibility of scale up.

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